

Novel Geometric Series for Application of Cryptography

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Abstract: This paper presents a novel geometric series along with theorems. These theorems and its results can be used as an application in computing and cryptography to develop algorithms like RSA algorithm and Elliptic Curve Cryptography.

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1. Introduction

Geometric series played a vital role in differential and integral calculus at the earlier stage of development and still continues as an important part of the study in science, engineering, management and its applications. In this article, a new geometric series [1-9] is constructed for application [10, 11] of computing science.

2. Novel Geometric Series

In today's world, the growing complexity of mathematical and computational modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical and combinatorial equations for solving today's scientific problems and challenges. In this section, novel theorems are formulated using the technique of traditional geometric progression [1-9].

Theorem 2.1 : Let R be a system of real numbers and $p, q \in R$.

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^{(p+q)i} &= \frac{x^{n(p+q)} - 1}{x^{(p+q)} - 1}, & (ii) \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^{(p*q)i} &= \frac{x^{n(p*q)} - 1}{x^{(p*q)} - 1}, \\ (iii) \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^{(p/q)i} &= \frac{x^{n(p/q)} - 1}{x^{(p/q)} - 1}, & (ii) \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^{(p\%q)i} &= \frac{x^{n(p\%q)} - 1}{x^{(p\%q)} - 1}, \end{aligned}$$

where $x^{p+q} \neq 1, x^{p+q} \neq 0^0, x^{p*q} \neq 1, x^{p*q} \neq 0^0, x^{p/q} \neq 1, x^{p/q} \neq 0^0, x^{p\%q} \neq 1, x^{p\%q} \neq 0^0$, and the arithmetic operators $+, *, /$, and $\%$ denote addition, multiplication, division, and remainder respectively.

Proof. Let us prove this theorem by the equality given below:

$$y^n = y^n \Rightarrow y^n = (y-1)y^{n-1} + y^{n-1} \Rightarrow y^n = (y-1)y^{n-1} + (y-1)y^{n-2} + y^{n-2}.$$

If we continue this expansion again and again, we can obtain the following series.

$$y^n = (y-1)y^{n-1} + (y-1)y^{n-2} + (y-1)y^{n-3} + \dots + (y-1)y + (y-1)y^0 + y^0.$$

$$i. e., \quad y^n - 1 = (y-1)(y^{n-1} + y^{n-2} + y^{n-3} + \dots + y + 1). \quad (1)$$

From the expansion (1), we obtain the series $\sum_{j=0}^{n-1} y^j = \frac{y^n - 1}{y - 1}, y \neq 1.$ (2)

If $y = x^{p+q}$ is substituted in the series (2), then we conclude that

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^{(p+q)i} = \frac{x^{n(p+q)} - 1}{x^{p+q} - 1}, x^{p+q} \neq 1 \text{ and } x^{p+q} \neq 0^0. \quad (3)$$

If $y = x^{p*q}$ is substituted in the series (2), then we conclude that

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^{(p*q)i} = \frac{x^{n(p*q)} - 1}{x^{p*q} - 1}, x^{p*q} \neq 1 \text{ and } x^{p*q} \neq 0^0. \quad (4)$$

If $y = x^{p/q}$ is substituted in the series (2), then we conclude that

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^{(p/q)i} = \frac{x^{n(p/q)} - 1}{x^{p/q} - 1}, x^{p/q} \neq 1 \text{ and } x^{p/q} \neq 0^0. \quad (5)$$

If $y = x^{p\%q}$ is substituted in the series (2), then we conclude that

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^{(p\%q)i} = \frac{x^{n(p\%q)} - 1}{x^{p\%q} - 1}, x^{p\%q} \neq 1 \text{ and } x^{p\%q} \neq 0^0. \quad (6)$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

The above-mentioned results can be used as an application in computing and cryptography to develop algorithms like RSA algorithm and Elliptic Curve Cryptography.

3. Conclusion

Computing science is a rapidly growing multi-disciplinary area where science, engineering, information technology, management and its collaborations use advance computing capabilities to understand and solve the most complex real life problems. In this article, a new geometric series is constituted for application of computing science.

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